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Efficient autoencoder pipeline for discovering high entropy alloys with molecular dynamics data

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Abstract

In this work, we utilize computationally efficient molecular dynamics simulations to create a machine learning pipeline for discovery of crystalline multi-component alloys. We employ high-quality interatomic potentials to create a dataset of NiFeCr structures and apply crystal diffusion variational autoencoder to maximize their mechanical properties, i.e. bulk modulus. As part of the experiment, we utilize local search coupled with classical interatomic potentials to explore the local structure space and show that utilization of this procedure greatly improves optimization capability of the neural model. We also expand the model with an extra submodule, which attains 42% improvement on modeling the crystalline phase of the structures. Ultimately, we verify the global stability of the created structures with quantum mechanical calculation methods.

1. Introduction

Discovery of novel materials involves both gathering experimental data and *in silico* modeling. Developments in machine learning largely benefit materials science, as neural networks have been applied to processing structure graphs (Choudhary and DeCost 2021, Gasteiger *et al* 2022a, 2022b). The amount of publicly available crystal structure data is growing rapidly (Jain *et al* 2013, Kirklin *et al* 2015). Material structure databases are of significance for the development of the field, as the high-fidelity *ab-initio* methods such as density functional theory (DFT) simulations bear large computational cost. To avoid the computational bottleneck, especially in the prototyping stage of design, one might resort to more efficient numerical solutions, such as molecular dynamics (MDs) simulations. MD employs numerical solutions to Newton's equations, facilitating the analysis of the dynamic evolution of atoms by treating them as interacting particles. MD simulations depend on the precise estimation of forces between atoms, acknowledging the intricate nature of atomic interactions in reality. In MD simulations, interatomic potentials, and mathematical formulations employed to approximate force fields, play a crucial role. Notably, recent advancements have explored the use of neural networks to enhance the accuracy of these interatomic potentials (Lot *et al* 2020, Batzner *et al* 2022). This work focuses on leveraging MD in conjunction with variational autoencoders to streamline the optimization of material properties, particularly in the case of multi-component alloys.

The experimental discovery of alloys containing multiple elements is inherently challenging due to the vast amount of possible compositional and structural combinations. Only two decades ago, a novel alloying technique emerged, proposing to mix multiple chemical elements in relatively high concentrations—the emergent structures are known as high-entropy alloys (HEAs) (Cantor *et al* 2004, Yeh *et al* 2004). This innovation has given rise to a new class of materials with exceptional properties, e.g. corrosion resistance or type-II superconductivity (Wu *et al* 2016, Xiao *et al* 2023). Consequently, there exists a multitude of potential

HEAs, each differing in the number of unique constituent chemical element types (e.g. binary, ternary, quaternary, and quinary alloys) and their respective weight percentages, making them a fascinating subject for study. The complexity of the problem is further heightened by the potential existence of multiple crystalline phases (CPs) in a given HEA with a specified composition. In materials science, crystal phase refers to the specific arrangement of atoms in a crystalline material, determining its unique structural properties. Due to the challenging and time-consuming nature of discovering novel HEAs with exceptional properties through experimentation and DFT, an alternative approach could involve utilizing generative deep learning.

Usage of diffusion variational autoencoders for material generation has been proposed by Xie *et al* (2022), who introduced the crystal graph diffusion variational autoencoder (CDVAE), and later followed by Zeni *et al* (2024). Previously to Xie *et al* (2022) variational autoencoders have been successfully used to process molecular graphs (Gebauer *et al* 2019), which, however, are not periodic and thus allow for a less structured approach. In essence, neural models designed for crystal structure processing must consider the periodic nature of crystals. In practical terms, a segment of the crystal is simulated under the assumption that it repeats indefinitely along three directions in space. The modeled region is commonly referred to as a 'supercell'. CDVAE has been successfully used to explore the composition space and discover new structures in the context of two-dimensional and superconducting materials (Lyngby and Thygesen 2022, Wines *et al* 2023). However, searching for HEAs requires us to consider the CP of the material in hand. A computational approach for identifying the CP of a HEA across various compositions is known as calculation of phase diagrams (CALPHADs). For instance, in a HEA such as NiFeCr with three chemical elements, CALPHAD determines the stable CP as the composition varies in terms of the percentage of each constituent element. In the case of NiFeCr, the material benchmarked in this paper, CALPHAD indicates that it should exhibit either a face-centered cubic (FCC) or body-centered cubic (BCC) CP (Lee *et al* 2001, Wu *et al* 2017). Hence, we must take a distinct approach to composition search within a HEA with specific constituent element types.

In this paper, we apply CDVAE in a workflow that involves obtaining data from classical interatomic potentials, elaborated in figure 1. In the specific case of NiFeCr, we generated an MD-based dataset comprising various compositions, including binary alloys, with CP determined using the CALPHAD method (Lee *et al* 2001, Wu *et al* 2017). This dataset was subsequently utilized to train the CDVAE model. NiFeCr was chosen due to its well-characterized phase behavior, the availability of validated interatomic potentials (Lee *et al* 2001, Wu *et al* 2017), and prior DFT studies confirming its stability at zero temperature (Wróbel *et al* 2015).

Next, we enhanced the CDVAE model by incorporating a fully connected (FC) neural network for CP classification—the resulting model is called P-CDVAE standing for Phase-CDVAE. This adjustment improved considerably the denoising task's performance and, as a result, better modeling of structures' CP. Afterwards, the model was used to explore the ternary composition space and generate new materials. The stability of the newly generated materials was assessed by calculating their formation energies using DFT. The results were in great agreement with other DFT-based methods aimed at the same study (Wróbel *et al* 2015).

Ultimately, we developed a local search framework that, in essence, seeks the optimal value of property within a given configuration of specific composition by manipulating atomic ordering and utilizing feedback from MD simulations. This method was employed to provide training data of the initial training dataset by incorporating the optimized mechanical properties, i.e. bulk modulus, for each data point in the test set identifying the ultimate optimized configuration regarding stability and mechanical properties. In summary, our primary contributions to this study are as follows:

- We applied CDVAE to a machine-learning workflow for generating crystal structures and optimizing their properties. Our approach utilizes efficient classical interatomic potentials to produce training data and assess the adequacy of sampled structures.
- We generated a dataset for ternary NiFeCr alloys, encompassing various atomic orderings of given compositions, and used CDVAE to discover new structures. Ultimately, we assessed the global stability of the generated structures with DFT simulations.
- We enhanced the exploration of the optimization space by crafting improved structures by local search coupled with MD. This facilitated optimization and enabled the model to enhance the bulk modulus of 59% examples to be higher than the 90th percentile of the features among those crafted structures.
- We improved the reconstruction performance of the autoencoder by training it to predict the crystal phase of structures before sampling. This reduced the distance function that evaluates the modeling of CP geometry by up to 42%.

2. Related work

Geometric graph neural networks (GNNs) for molecular graphs. In recent years, several GNNs have been developed with a specific emphasis on processing molecular graphs. These models employ graph geometry, representing atoms as nodes and their interatomic distances as edges, to generate various types of embeddings. For instance, some models focus on edge lengths, such as SchNet (Schütt *et al* 2017) and Physnet Unke and Meuwly (2019), while others consider both edge lengths and angles between them, e.g. DimeNet (Gasteiger *et al* 2022b), GemNet-T (Gasteiger *et al* 2022a), and AliGNN (Choudhary and DeCost 2021). In its advanced version, GemNet-Q (Gasteiger *et al* 2022a) goes a step further by incorporating torsion angles, which correspond to triplets of consecutive edges, to create positional embeddings. The autoencoder used in this work utilizes DimeNet++ as the encoder and GemNet-T as the decoder (Xie *et al* 2022).

Diffusion models for chemical structures. Generative models have been applied to the materials science context extensively (Hoffmann *et al* 2019, Long *et al* 2021, Zhao *et al* 2021, Ren *et al* 2022). Diffusion autoencoders are a class of generative models that have shown great performance at generating structured data by iteratively refining them (Cai *et al* 2020, Dhariwal and Nichol 2021, Shi *et al* 2021). They manage various degrees of noise by optimizing a score function that responds to the distortion of data, e.g. through the physics-inspired Langevin dynamics (Song and Ermon 2019). The interpretations of score functions may vary, depending on the specifics of the problem and experimental decisions: a likelihood-based approach utilizes the probability distribution modeled by the network to maximize the likelihood of denoised data. CDVAE utilizes direct prediction of forces acting. There are various approaches to modeling chemical entities with diffusion models: E(3) equivariant diffusion model, for example, uses the notion of likelihood (Hoogeboom *et al* 2022).

Quantum mechanical material discovery. The quest for stable materials with exceptional properties poses a significant challenge when exclusively relying on quantum mechanical methods (Oganov *et al* 2019). Efforts have been made to tackle this challenge through various approaches, including evolutionary algorithms (Glass *et al* 2006, Wang *et al* 2012), random sampling (Pickard and Needs 2011), and the exploration of substitutional alloying within already established stable materials (Hautier *et al* 2011). Among these methods, cluster expansion (CE) (Wu *et al* 2016) techniques utilize quantum mechanical calculations to identify ground-state stable structures in medium-entropy alloys, and they are typically applied to alloys containing up to three components. However, it is worth noting that these methods may struggle with multi-component

complex materials and the presence of multiple CPs and effect of configurational entropy (Wróbel *et al* 2015, Anand *et al* 2016)—which is negligible below the room temperature. In contrast, generative models offer a faster and more efficient approach when exploring the vast compositional space of materials.

3. Methods

3.1. CDVAE model

CDVAE. Our approach to searching for new NiFeCr alloys revolves around the use of CDVAE (Xie *et al* 2022). The model is composed of DimeNet++ (Gasteiger *et al* 2022b) as the encoder and GemNet-dT (Gasteiger *et al* 2022a) as the decoder. As shown in figure 2(a), the model is trained on denoising task—the input structure is first passed through the encoder, then it undergoes a random perturbation in terms of node coordinates and atom types. The loss function includes the distance the nodes have moved from their assigned position, the discrepancy in atom types between the original structure and the reconstructed one, and Kullback–Leibler divergence. The decoder produces two outputs for each element. Firstly, the score function that governs the denoising is computed. This output is treated as a set of forces that act upon the atoms, and their coordinates are adjusted accordingly. Secondly, the atom types are predicted—this way, the model can correct atom-type errors created by the noise. Creation of new structures (sampling), involves choosing a random feature vector and using the decoder to iteratively refine the atoms’ positions and types with annealed Langevin dynamics (Song and Ermon 2019). The key feature of this approach is that, apart from the informed changes made by the model, Gaussian noise is added with every step. As the magnitude of the injected noise is gradually decreased, the process approaches convergence.

Apart from the two GNNs, the model is equipped with a couple of FC submodules that all take the latent vector as the input. As they act on the structure’s scalar representation, they predict different structure-level features before the decoder resolves the atom-level features—coordinates and atom types. The remaining components of the loss function are associated with errors made by individual FC submodules. Those serve several purposes:

Initialization of sampled structures. Langevin dynamics is conducted within a supercell of a fixed size and on a fixed number of atoms. The sampling step of the model is depicted in figure 2(b). To initialize the structure for denoising, three FC modules are used: *FC-n-atom* predicts the number of atoms in a structure, *FC-lattice* predicts the lattice lengths of lattice vectors and the angles between them, while *FC-composition* provides a prior estimation of the content of each element in the structure. With the aforementioned estimates available, initialization is a straightforward process of sampling a known number of atoms: each of

them is assigned a random position within the supercell space; atom types are chosen randomly from the distribution provided by *FC-composition*.

Property optimization. *FC-property* predicts the target property from the feature vector. Having trained it, one can use a gradient descent algorithm, e.g. Adam (Kingma and Ba 2015) to modify the feature vector with the target of optimizing a property of choice, while the model's parameters are frozen.

Improving the modeling. We propose to equip CDVAE with an additional layer: *FC-phase*. The purpose of this layer is to provide additional knowledge about the CP of the structure. As was shown in figure SM. A2(b), NiFeCr structures form purely single-phase (either FCC or BCC) metallic crystals, based solely on the elementary composition. We train the model to explicitly predict whether the structure is FCC or BCC. We add this information to the decoder's input: the predicted phase is combined with types of individual atoms when passed to the decoder's embedding layer, e.g. we allow the decoder to produce a different embedding for 'nickel atom in a BCC structure' and 'nickel atom in an FCC structure'. This addition is aimed at helping the model assess the correct relative positions of atoms that depend predominantly on the crystal phase. From a graph modeling perspective, it is a high-level description of edge lengths and angles expected to be seen in the decoded structure. The variant of CDVAE equipped with *FC-phase* will be referred to as P-CDVAE. Although the core CDVAE model operates statistically, our framework incorporates physics-based guidance through multiple stages. The training dataset was constructed using CALPHAD-informed phase stability at the ground state (Wróbel *et al* 2015, Wu *et al* 2017), and we integrated a crystal phase prediction module to embed metallurgical knowledge into the generation process. Additionally, the model's sampling relies on Langevin Dynamics (Song and Ermon 2019), providing a physics-inspired mechanism for denoising the generated configurations to the lowest energy state possible.

3.2. Dataset creation

The dataset consists of NiFeCr crystal structures, as well as binary combinations: NiFe, FeCr, FeCr. All of them are either FCC or BCC structures. To represent a structure of either kind, one needs a minimum of a cell of 2-atoms, repeated periodically and creating the final 'supercell'. To capture a larger region within the structure (a large enough supercell), one can include multiple unit cells within—we opt to use $3 \times 3 \times 3$ unit cells within a supercell, which amounts to 54 atoms. The benefit of modeling larger supercells is twofold—it can express more complex structures, while also allowing to search for different elementary compositions at a finer resolution. MD simulations were conducted with the LAMMPS package (Thompson *et al* 2022). To capture the relaxed structures along with their corresponding energies and forces, we employed the conjugate gradient (CG) algorithm at zero temperature. The resulting configurations were then used to calculate the bulk modulus. Classical interatomic potentials developed by Wu *et al* (2017) and Lee *et al* (2001), based on the modified embedded atom method (MEAM), are employed for NiFe, NiCr, FeCr, and NiFeCr alloys. These potentials have been validated against experimental data and DFT calculations for accurately reproducing the thermodynamic and mechanical properties of these alloys. first, we choose a range of elementary compositions. Next, for each of them, we create 20 structures with random orders of atoms within. This also enables the inclusion of ordered phases in the dataset in an unbiased way (section A.6). The ordering of atoms in HEAs plays a crucial role in the properties of those materials. The dataset created this way will be referred to as 'NiFeCr-Random'. We also create an analogous dataset of $2 \times 2 \times 2$, named 'NiFeCr-Small' for analysis. Details of MD and DFT calculations are presented in the appendix section A.6. The dataset generation process using MD simulations is notably efficient regarding runtime. Although it involves numerous calls to the MD package, it can still produce a dataset of 1200 configurations in approximately two hours. In contrast, generating the same dataset with DFT would require 3–4 h per configuration on an A100 80GB NVIDIA GPU for a self-consistent calculation only. For calculating mechanical properties, such as elastic constants, DFT would be nearly ten times more time-consuming. The code for generating datasets based on molecular dynamics is available in the GitHub repository by Dorabati 2023.

Crafting examples with local search. The dataset comprises structures obtained in MD simulations with randomly chosen ordering for different atom types. Mechanical properties of alloys are largely affected by chemical short-range ordering of atoms (Zhang *et al* 2020, Naghdi *et al* 2023). We hypothesize that the short-range patterns that contribute to the highest bulk modulus consist of local structures that cannot be easily obtained at random. To provide the model with such examples, we extended the dataset with structures crafted in an informed way. For that, we implemented a local search that involves swapping positions of pairs of atoms to optimize the bulk modulus with feedback from MD for each considered configuration. During each iteration, 20 random atom transpositions are tried, each followed by relaxation of the structure and computation of the bulk modulus. The code for training the P-CDVAE model and performing local search is available in the GitHub repository by Kaszuba 2023.

Table 1. Reconstruction scores of CDVAE on carbon, NiFeCr-Small and NiFeCr-Random datasets.

Dataset	Match rate	FP dist
Carbon	66.2%	0.2603
NiFeCr-Small	30.0%	0.1758
NiFeCr-Random	6.4%	0.1358

Table 2. Reconstruction scores of CDVAE trained on NiFeCr-Random and instances of P-CDVAE trained on NiFeCr-Random or NiFeCr-LS. Reconstruction is evaluated against the common part of the test set, which is the test set of NiFeCr-Random. The metrics used were fingerprint distance, G-distance, and CP G-distance.

Model	FP dist	G-dist	CP G-dist
CDVAE-Random	0.1358	0.3618	0.0984
P-CDVAE-Random	0.1039	0.3513	0.0691
P-CDVAE-LS	0.0823	0.3521	0.0560

For the next iteration, the structure with the highest value of this property is chosen, among the ground structure and the created ones. Experiments have been conducted on 3 datasets. NiFeCr-LS is a dataset which, apart from all structures from NiFeCr-Random, includes structures that have undergone 20 local search iterations as described: 10% of examples from NiFeCr-Random’s training, validation, and test examples were randomly chosen, optimized this way, and added to their respective partitions of the data. The changes in the mean property during the local search are shown in figure SM. A3.

4. Experiments

4.1. Reconstruction

We evaluate the model’s capability to encode and reconstruct the structures. This task provides valuable insights into the deterministic nature of the sampling process. We use *pymatgen’s StructureMatcher* class. We use error tolerances of *StructureMatcher* originally used in Xie *et al* (2022). We also test Cartesian distance between structure fingerprints produced by *pymatgen’s CrystalNN* tool, which we deem useful as they give a measure of similarity without the need to correctly match the structure. First, we compare the reconstruction performance of CDVAE to the carbon dataset, investigated in Xie *et al* (2022). The match rate is higher than in the original experiment, which can be attributed to the double number of steps we use in Langevin dynamics. We also assess reconstruction performance of NiFeCr-Small, which is a variant with a similar number of atoms in a supercell (up to 24 for carbon and 16 for NiFeCr-Small), and NiFeCr-Random, which possesses significantly larger structures. The results can be seen in table 1. Committing to larger structures makes the match unlikely and thus, the sampling procedure is not deterministic. The results also point to a qualitative difference between the NiFeCr datasets and carbon. Fingerprint distances suggest that, on average, the reconstructions of NiFeCr structures are composed of sites with similar local neighborhoods. This, however, does not translate to high match rates. We hypothesize that the relative position and orientation of those local clusters are different, which inevitably compromises the global match, especially for NiFeCr-Random. Nonetheless, even for NiFeCr-Small, it could be attributed to permutational freedom of NiFeCr structures. The dichotomy between the local action of variational autoencoders and the global integrity of reconstruction has been pinpointed by Xie *et al* (2022).

Next, we compare the models trained on datasets composed of 54-atom structures: either NiFeCr-Random or NiFeCr-LS. For brevity, we refer to the experiments by the type of the model and data—e.g. P-CDVAE-LS is a P-CDVAE trained on NiFeCr-LS. The match rate is disregarded in comparison. Instead, we aim to evaluate the reconstruction of the geometry under which atoms are distributed, aside from the elements that those atoms represent. For that, we use G-vectors. G-vectors are atomic fingerprints that encode the local environment with regard to both the types of nearest atoms and geometric features—lengths of the edges and angles between them. Based on G-vectors, we compute G-distances between two structures, which is explained in detail in the appendix section A.5. We also introduce CP G-distances by disregarding the atomic types during the computation of G-vectors—those descriptors match the geometric environment of individual atoms. The reconstruction of the models trained on 54-atom NiFeCr structures has been compared with regard to *CrystalNN* fingerprint distance and both G-vector distances (table 2). Notably, both P-CDVAE models showed significant improvement in CP G-distance compared to CDVAE: 29% and 42%, respectively. This suggests an improvement in the modeling of the crystal phase.

4.2. Material generation

The P-CDVAE model succeeded in achieving similar results compared to pure quantum-based calculations (Wróbel *et al* 2015) for the generation task. The success of this task depends on various factors, including the performance of the generative model framework and the reconstruction task, among others. As a result, we conducted an evaluation of both CDVAE and P-CDVAE in the reconstruction and generation task to determine their respective performance, ultimately choosing generated materials from P-CDVAE for subsequent DFT validation due to its enhanced capability in denoising the structures within their ground truth CP (more details in appendix section A.3). In order to achieve this, latent vectors from a multidimensional Gaussian distribution were utilized to query the CDVAE and P-CDVAE models. This process resulted in the generation of 500 structures, encompassing a significant portion of both binary and ternary alloy composition spaces.

In constructing the training dataset for the ternary NiFeCr alloy system, we relied on configurations validated by Wu *et al* (2017) and made slight adjustments to the compositions to slightly broaden the dataset. However, due to computational constraints (DFT validations), only 500 configurations were generated during the generation task, resulting in a less dense sampling of the Fe-rich region, which was reflected in the optimization and generation outcomes. Had we generated a larger number of samples, the Fe-rich region would have been more densely populated, addressing the issue of its underrepresentation in the dataset.

The distribution of generated structures in terms of their composition is shown in figure SM A1(c). Afterwards, we did spin-polarized DFT calculations, and based on the formation energy results, we found great agreement with the CE method, which is purely based on quantum mechanical calculations, in terms of the stability of the materials for NiFeCr structures (Wróbel *et al* 2015). Both P-CDVAE and CE agree on the stable compositions of ternary NiFeCr and their binary alloys. Figures 3(a) and (b) shows the convex hull plot for binary FeCr/NiFe alloys in the dashed line. In materials science, a convex hull (of stable structures) is a representation of the most thermodynamically stable compositions within an alloy system. It is determined by plotting the formation energies, calculated using high-fidelity methods like DFT, of known stable materials against the alloy's composition, providing insights into optimal alloy compositions for stability. For example, in the case of NiFe, P-CDVAE generated a new stable material (FeNi_5) with formation energy laying on the convex hull and many meta-stable materials (which could be stable under special thermodynamical situations such as high pressure and temperature) with a negative formation energy. all materials with a positive formation energy are considered unstable. The same goes with ternary NiFeCr (figure 3(c)), where our model found stable materials (blue dots) in the ternary composition space. This benchmarks the method designed in this work promising for the study of higher than three component alloys. Here, the DFT validation provides insights into the ground-state (zero-temperature) stability of the generated structures by evaluating their formation energies. However, these calculations do not account for finite-temperature effects such as vibrational or configurational entropy, which are important for experimental phase stability. Extending the framework to include temperature-dependent free energy contributions is an important direction for future work.

4.3. Optimization

We employed the models we obtained to optimize the bulk modulus. Two previously tested instances of P-CDVAE were used—one trained on NiFeCr-Random and one trained on NiFeCr-LS. To provide the same experimental conditions for both models, we used the test partition of NiFeCr-Random (composed of 327 structures) as the initial optimization points. The structures from the test set were encoded and the obtained

Table 3. Results of property optimization with (a) the model trained on the dataset of randomly initialized NiFeCr structures and (b) dataset with addition of structures. Latent vectors that describe structures have been optimized with the Adam algorithm. At the given steps of this process, they were utilized to produce crystal structures. For each of those steps, the number of correctly decoded structures is shown, along with the statistics of their properties. The mean value of the property is shown for all correctly decoded structures and for 10 structures with the highest value of the property.

(a) NiFeCr-Random				(b) NiFeCr-20			
Step	Mean B	Mean B (top 10)	Correct	Step	Mean B	Mean B (top 10)	Correct
Initial	181.7	192.0	327	Initial	181.7	192.0	327
200	181.4	193.1	237	200	181.7	192.9	265
500	181.7	193.3	225	500	182.4	193.0	247
1000	181.1	193.8	178	1000	185.4	194.4	199
1500	182.8	193.8	129	1500	189.8	195.0	186
2500	185.8	193.3	45	2500	193.0	196.5	124

latent vectors were optimized with the Adam algorithm (with a learning rate 0.001). Each step of optimizing a latent vector involves querying the *FC-property* network and using back-propagation to maximize the bulk modulus. The encodings were used to sample new structures at several optimization stages: after 200, 500, 1000, 1500, and 2500 steps. The bulk moduli of sampled structures were assessed with MDs simulations, as described in section 3.2. MD simulations were also employed to rule out the incorrectly denoised structures—we require that, after the simulation converges, per-atom energy is not higher than the threshold set by the highest per-atom energy found in the training data. Additionally, we require that the output of the neural model is already close to convergence—the structure’s total energy can be at most 10 eV above the final threshold. This is to ensure that structures passed to MD are already close to the relaxed state—otherwise, passing structures that do not meet these criteria may cause MD simulations that do not converge, or, having reached the maximum number of iterations, yield unrelaxed structures and return anomalous values of the target property. As encodings are optimized with a simple goal to maximize the prediction of a FC network, the moment when most of them cease to translate into structures that fit these criteria marks the end of the experiment.

Results. Table 3 shows the amount of correctly decoded structures, as well as the values of elastic moduli present in the population of optimized structures at consecutive stages—those include the mean bulk modulus among all correct structures and the mean bulk modulus of 10 best structures present in the population. P-CDVAE, trained on NiFeCr-Random showed little capability to optimize the bulk elastic modulus (table 3). The inclusion of examples crafted with local search during training allowed for more effective optimization by the model trained on NiFeCr-LS. Table A1 shows the percentage of initial structures whose optimization achieved bulk modulus of value thresholds during one of the sampling steps. For the model trained on NiFeCr-Random, the thresholds were based on the distribution of the training part of NiFeCr-Random. For the model trained on NiFeCr-LS, the thresholds were set only by those training examples, which were the product of local search, making for a more demanding baseline. Nevertheless, the percentage of structures optimized above the thresholds was higher for this model. The model trained on NiFeCr-LS also found the new maximum value of the bulk modulus, 197.26 GPa, compared to the highest one obtained during local search: 196.58 GPa. Figure 4 shows the highest property values of property for each composition obtained during optimization for both models. The model trained on NiFeCr-LS generated structures with high bulk modulus across various compositions.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a computationally efficient pipeline for generating crystal structures has been proposed. The experimental procedure employed classical interatomic potentials to generate the data and assess the quality of the outputs yielded by the autoencoder. MD simulations were used to relax the created structures further and predict the bulk modulus. The feasibility of the proposed experimental procedure depends on the availability of interatomic potentials for the structures considered. The development of new interatomic potentials is a trend that benefits the applicability of MD. As part of the data creation procedure, local search was used to craft examples in an informed way. This was done by changing the order of atoms to maximize the target property. The addition of 10% of structures crafted with local search to the base dataset proved crucial for the optimization efficiency. This speaks to the importance of conditioning data to convey knowledge relevant to the problem at hand.

Figure 4. The highest values of bulk modulus of structures generated during optimization, by composition. (a) Shows the results for the model trained on NiFeCr-Random, (b) the results for the model trained on NiFeCr-LS.

NiFeCr structures form two distinct CPs. Apart from that, the template of the structure does not vary significantly. The prior estimation of crystal phase and its use in diffusion, allowed for a better reconstruction of this template. The reconstruction of 54-atom structures was not faithful enough to match the reconstructed examples to their ground truth counterparts with the *StructureMatcher* Ong *et al* (2013). Even for 16-atom structures, faithful reconstruction posed a significant challenge. Therefore, it must be noted that the sampling performed by the model was not a deterministic process. Nonetheless, neural optimization was successful. The reconstruction scores achieved by the model suggest that the discrepancies between the encoded and decoded structures stem mostly from the permutation of atoms inside, while the spatial distribution of nodes is accurate. It can be hypothesized that the results could be improved by employing changes that facilitate faithful, global reconstruction of the atomic order. It is especially challenging for a diffusion model, whose principle is to model the structure bottom-up from local interactions Xie *et al* (2022). To better preserve the input structure, one could experiment with the part of CDVAE responsible for the assignment of atom types to every node or ensure that the encoding is descriptive enough to reconstruct it by increasing the size of the dataset, the length of the latent vector, and the length of interactions modeled by the employed GNNs. It is possible that for optimal reconstruction of alloy supercells with the proposed size, a hierarchical graph autoencoder would be more appropriate than a diffusion model. Lastly, the P-CDVAE method can be generalized to handle intermetallic phases and solid-solid two-phase coexistence regions by explicitly augmenting the dataset with intermetallic configurations and also systematically increasing the temperature of the dataset configurations up to the melting point, verifying their phase stability through CALPHAD, and retraining the model. In this approach, atomic distortions induced by thermal motion naturally embed finite-temperature effects into the latent space. A more robust extension to perform physics-based alloy predictions (Fedorov *et al* 2023), would involve incorporating an explicit temperature-dependent module into the model to guide generation and optimization tasks at specific temperatures.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: https://github.com/grzegorzkaszuba/allogen_cdvae and <https://github.com/Amirhossein4131/AlloGen.git>.

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Figure A1. Material generation performance. (a) and (b) Summarize both CDVAE and P-CDVAE models' ability to denoise newly generated structures to the *ground truth* CP, determined by CALPHAD calculations shown in figure 2. (c) Demonstrates the distribution of the newly generated materials w.r.t the points covered in the initial dataset. In (d) and (e) the stable materials, validated in DFT, are shown for all the binary materials, and the corresponding ternary plot is presented in (g).

Appendix/supplemental material

A.1. Model hyperparameters

We use the same model hyperparameters for CDVAE as in Xie *et al* (2022). The encoder is DimeNet++ with 128 hidden channels and 4 interaction blocks. The decoder is GemNet-dT, a variant of the model designed for direct force prediction. FC submodules are composed of 2 hidden layers, 256 channels each. The model has 5.1 million parameters in total.

A.2. Execution time of experiments

MD simulations were conducted using LAMMPS on an Intel i7 11 800-H CPU. The creation of data with local search involved optimizing a total of 183 structures, and conducting 400 relaxations and bulk modulus computations. The wall time of the procedure was 16 h and 3 min. The autoencoder optimization was done on an NVIDIA A100 GPU. Sampling involved Langevin dynamics with noise being annealed throughout 50 steps. We increased the number of model inferences on each step to 200 (compared to 100 in Xie *et al* (2022)). The initial run on P-CDVAE involved sampling at 7 different breakpoints at varying intervals, 2 of which were disregarded. Sampling of a full batch (128 structures). Structures generated during optimization 7 h and 22 min. Relaxation of those structures with LAMMPS, including those far from the relaxed state and therefore disregarded in the analysis, took 6 h and 34 min.

A.3. Generation task

Figures A1(a) and (b) show the CDVAE and P-CDVAE performance in denoising the newly generated materials into the correct crystal phases, evaluated with the Ovito package—black lines indicate the correct boundary between BCC and FCC phases, as described in the literature (Wróbel *et al* 2015). Qualitatively, the P-CDVAE model performs better in terms of correct crystal phase, which is in correspondence with the reconstruction scores in the section 4.1. We show the distribution of the 500 generated configurations against the points in the dataset in figure A.3(c), which shows that the vast part of the ternary phase diagram is covered. Afterwards, we did spin-polarized DFT calculations, and based on the formation energy results, we found great agreement with the CE method in terms of the stability of the materials for NiFeCr structures (Wróbel *et al* 2015). This benchmarks the method designed in this work promising for the study of higher than three component alloys.

A.4. Optimization task

Table A1. The fraction of structures generated in optimization whose bulk modulus falls within the top 10%, 20% or 30% of values present in the training data. For NiFeCr-Random, the optimized are compared to the entire train set. For NiFeCr-LS, only the portion of the training data crafted with local search is considered for comparison.

Model	Top 10%	Top 20%	Top 30%
NiFeCr-Random	22%	32%	50%
NiFeCr-20	59%	65%	68%

A.5. Reconstruction scores with Behler–Parrinello (BP) vectors

To cover the random ordering of the atoms at a specific point in the composition space, we need to choose relatively large examples that have the freedom to form arbitrary permutations of all the atoms. However, we have observed that perfect reconstruction of the entire structure is unlikely. Therefore, we use BP (Behler and Parrinello 2007) vectors, which are embeddings of local geometry for each atom, describing its local environment, to measure the similarity between the ground truth and the reconstructed configurations. In this work, PANNA: properties from artificial neural network architectures (Lot *et al* 2020), is used as an external package for calculation of the modified version of BP (mBP) descriptors (Smith *et al* 2017). The mBP representation generates a fixed-size vector, $G[s]$, the ‘G-vector’, for each atom in each configuration of the dataset. Each G-vector describes the environment of the corresponding atom of the configuration to which it belongs, up to a cutoff radius R_c . In terms of the distances R_{ij} and R_{ik} from the atom i to its neighbors j and k and the angles between the neighbors θ_{jik} . The radial and angular G-vectors are given by:

$$G_i^{\text{rad}}[s] = \sum_{i \neq j} e^{-\eta(R_{ij}-R_s)^2} f_c(R_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

$$G_i^{\text{ang}}[s] = 2^{1-\zeta} \sum_{j,k \neq i} [1 + \cos(\theta_{jik} - \theta_s)]^\zeta \times e^{-\eta[\frac{1}{2}(R_{ij}+R_{ik})-R_s]^2} f_c(R_{ij}) f_c(R_{ik}) \quad (2)$$

where the smooth cutoff function (which includes the cutoff radius R_c) is given by:

$$f_c(R_{ij}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi R_{ij}}{R_c}\right) + 1 \right], & R_{ij} \leq R_c \\ 0, & R_{ij} > R_c \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and η , ζ , θ_s and R_s are parameters, different for the radial and angular parts. The choice of the cutoff value is made so that it covers up to three nearest neighbors of the center atom in the BCC NiFeCr, which has an average lattice constant of $a = 3 \text{ \AA}$, and thus the third nearest neighbor’s distance is $a \times \sqrt{2} = 4.24 \text{ \AA}$. This automatically covers up to the 4th nearest neighbor of the FCC crystal. We use Euclidean distance between G-vectors of two atoms as a measure of their dissimilarity. To assess the overall dissimilarity of two structures, we compute the minimum assignment between the G-vectors of their respective atoms. Then the average of the distances between all atom pairs in such assignment is taken, and we refer to that value as ‘G-distance’ between a pair of structures.

A.6. Dataset creation

MD specification. We create NiFeCr structures in a range of elementary compositions, validated to be stable based on MEAM interatomic potentials developed by Wu *et al* (2017) and Lee *et al* (2001). The mentioned MEAM potentials were validated by experimental data and CALPHADs calculations (for detailed information on the potentials see the references). Apart from the specific compositions studied in Wu *et al* (2017), we added very small noise to the compositions of stable structures (less than 2 atomic percent), such that the final trained model has seen more data. The dataset creation workflow is presented as a diagram in figure SM A2. and is available as in (<https://github.com/Amirhossein4131/AlloGen.git>). The dataset creation starts by creating a crystal matrix (either BCC or FCC structure), based on the composition. The initial matrix is selected based on the composition of the atoms as shown in figure SM A2.(b). Afterwards, the target structure with the specific composition is created by random substitution of second and third atom types with the first atom type in the matrix.

For each elementary composition, 20 random configurations of a given composition are added to the dataset. LAMMPS software (Thompson *et al* 2022) is used for the MD calculations, as well as the calculation of

the formation energies and the bulk modulus. The MD simulations mentioned in this work do not refer to time-evolving Newtonian dynamics. Instead, we performed CG relaxation at $T = 0$ K, and used the relaxed configurations to calculate the bulk modulus by applying small deformations and evaluating the resulting changes in total energy.

Dataset augmentation with local search. To augment the dataset with optimized property materials, 10% of examples from NiFeCr-Random's training, validation, and test examples were randomly chosen, optimized with the local search method explained in the main text, and added to their respective partitions of the data. Figure SM A3 shows the property optimizations versus local search iterations.

DFT validation. The DFT spin-polarized calculations were performed with the Vasp package (Kresse and Hafner 1993, Kresse and Furthmüller 1996a, 1996b), using PAW PBE exchange–correlation functional (Blöchl 1994, Kresse and Joubert 1999) and an initial magnetic moment of $\text{NIONS} \times 5.0$ (NIONS is the number of atoms in the cell). The Brillouin zone was sampled using a maximum k point spacing of 0.5 \AA^{-1} on Γ -centered Monkhorst–Pack grids (Monkhorst and Pack 1976) and plane-wave cutoff energy of 520 eV. Smearing with the spreading of 0.05 eV was introduced within the Methfessel–Paxton method (Methfessel and Paxton 1989) to help convergence.

Ordered phases. Our dataset was designed to include structural diversity by randomly reordering atomic positions for each composition multiple times, rather than explicitly inserting known ordered prototypes such as $L1_2$ or $L1_0$. This strategy ensures a broad sampling of both ordered and disordered configurations, giving the model the opportunity to learn from a wide range of atomic arrangements without biasing it toward pre-assumed ground states. While the precise ground-state ordering could later be determined through external evaluations such as DFT or MD-based local search, this approach preserves the

discovery-driven nature of the generative pipeline. To illustrate this, we include in figure SM A4. of the supplementary materials a representative subset of ordered-like structures that emerged from our random sampling process.

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References

- Anand G, Goodall R and Freeman C L 2016 Role of configurational entropy in body-centred cubic or face-centred cubic phase formation in high entropy alloys *Scr. Mater.* **124** 90–94
- Batzner S, Musaelian A, Sun L, Geiger M, Mailoa J P, Kornbluth M, Molinari N, Smidt T E and Kozinsky B 2022 E(3)-equivariant graph neural networks for data-efficient and accurate interatomic potentials *Nat. Commun.* **13** 2453
- Behler J and Parrinello M 2007 Generalized neural-network representation of high-dimensional potential-energy surfaces *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **98** 146401
- Blöchl P E 1994 Projector augmented-wave method *Phys. Rev. B* **50** 17953–79
- Cai R, Yang G, Averbuch-Elor H, Hao Z, Belongie S, Snively N and Hariharan B 2020 Learning gradient fields for shape generation (arXiv:2008.06520)
- Cantor B, Chang I T H, Knight P and Vincent A J B 2004 Microstructural development in equiatomic multicomponent alloys *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **375-377** 213–8
- Choudhary K and DeCost B 2021 Atomistic line graph neural network for improved materials property predictions *npj Comput. Mater.* **7** 185
- Dhariwal P and Nichol A 2021 Diffusion models beat gans on image synthesis (arXiv:2105.05233)
- Dorabati A N 2023 AlloGen: dataset generator based on molecular dynamics data (available at: <https://github.com/Amirhossein4131/AlloGen>)
- Fedorov M, Wróbel J S, London A J, Kurzydłowski K J, Fu C-C, Tadić T, Dudarev S L and Nguyen-Manh D 2023 Precipitation of Cr-rich clusters in Fe-Cr alloys: effects of irradiation from first principles modeling and experimental observations *J. Nucl. Mater.* **587** 154715
- Gasteiger J, Becker F and Günnemann S 2022a GemNet: universal directional graph neural networks for molecules (arXiv:2106.08903)
- Gasteiger J, Groß J and Günnemann S 2022b Directional message passing for molecular graphs (arXiv:2003.03123)

- Gebauer N W A, Gastegger M and Schütt K T 2019 *Symmetry-Adapted Generation of 3d Point Sets for the Targeted Discovery of Molecules* (Curran Associates Inc.)
- Glass C W, Oganov A R and Hansen N 2006 USPEX-evolutionary crystal structure prediction *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **175** 713–20
- Hautier G, Fischer C, Ehrlicher V, Jain A and Ceder G 2011 Data mined ionic substitutions for the discovery of new compounds *Inorg. Chem.* **50** 656–63
- Hoffmann J, Maestrati L, Sawada Y, Tang J, Sellier J M D and Bengio Y 2019 Data-driven approach to encoding and decoding 3-D crystal structures *CoRR* (arXiv:1909.00949)
- Hoogeboom E, Satorras V G, Vignac C and Welling M 2022 Equivariant diffusion for molecule generation in 3D (arXiv:2203.17003)
- Jain A et al 2013 Commentary: the materials project: a materials genome approach to accelerating materials innovation *APL Mater.* **1** 011002
- Kaszuba G 2023 *allogen_cdvae*: P-CDVAE for alloy generation (available at: https://github.com/grzegorzkaszuba/allogen_cdvae)
- Kingma D and Ba J 2015 Adam: a method for stochastic optimization *Int. Conf. on Learning Representations (ICLR)*
- Kirklin S, Saal J E, Meredig B, Thompson A, Doak J W, Aykol M, Rühl S and Wolverton C 2015 The open quantum materials database (OQMD): assessing the accuracy of DFT formation energies *npj Comput. Mater.* **1** 15010
- Kresse G and Furthmüller J 1996 Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **6** 15–50
- Kresse G and Furthmüller J 1996 Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set *Phys. Rev. B* **54** 11169–86
- Kresse G and Hafner J 1993 Ab initio molecular dynamics for liquid metals *Phys. Rev. B* **47** 558–61
- Kresse G and Joubert D 1999 From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method *Phys. Rev. B* **59** 1758–75
- Lee B-J, Shim J-H and Park H M 2001 A semi-empirical atomic potential for the Fe-Cr binary system *Calphad* **25** 527–34
- Long T, Fortunato N M, Opahle I, Zhang Y, Samathrakris I, Shen C, Gutfleisch O and Zhang H 2021 Constrained crystals deep convolutional generative adversarial network for the inverse design of crystal structures *npj Comput. Mater.* **7** 66
- Lot R, Pellegrini F, Shaidu Y and Küçükbenli E 2020 PANNA: properties from artificial neural network architectures *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **256** 107402
- Lyngby P and Thygesen K S 2022 Data-driven discovery of 2D materials by deep generative models *npj Comput. Mater.* **8** 232
- Methfessel M and Paxton A T 1989 High-precision sampling for Brillouin-zone integration in metals *Phys. Rev. B* **40** 3616–21
- Monkhorst H J and Pack J D 1976 Special points for brillouin-zone integrations *Phys. Rev. B* **13** 5188–92
- Naghdi A H, Karimi K, Poisvert A E, Esfandiarpour A, Alvarez R, Sobkowicz P, Alava M and Papanikolaou S 2023 Dislocation plasticity in equiatomic NiCoCr alloys: effect of short-range order *Phys. Rev. B* **107** 094109
- Oganov A R, Pickard C J, Zhu Q and Needs R J 2019 Structure prediction drives materials discovery *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **4** 331–48
- Ong S P, Richards W D, Jain A, Hautier G, Kocher M, Cholia S, Gunter D, Chevrier V L, Persson K A and Ceder G 2013 Python materials genomics (pymatgen): a robust, open-source python library for materials analysis *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **68** 314–9
- Pickard C J and Needs R J 2011 Ab initio random structure searching *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **23** 053201
- Ren Z et al 2022 An invertible crystallographic representation for general inverse design of inorganic crystals with targeted properties *Matter* **5** 314–35
- Schütt K T, Kindermans P-J, Sauceda H E, Chmiela S, Tkatchenko A and Müller K-R 2017 SchNet: a continuous-filter convolutional neural network for modeling quantum interactions (arXiv:1706.08566)
- Shi C, Luo S, Xu M and Tang J 2021 Learning gradient fields for molecular conformation generation *Proc. 38th Int. Conf. on Machine Learning (Proc. Machine Learning Research vol 139)*, ed M Meila and T Zhang (PMLR) pp 9558–68
- Smith J S, Isayev O and Roitberg A E 2017 ANI-1: an extensible neural network potential with DFT accuracy at force field computational cost *Chem. Sci.* **8** 3192–203
- Song Y and Ermon S 2019 Generative modeling by estimating gradients of the data distribution *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* vol 32, ed H Wallach, H Larochelle, A Beygelzimer, F d' Alché-Buc, E Fox and R Garnett (Curran Associates, Inc.)
- Thompson A P et al 2022 LAMMPS - a flexible simulation tool for particle-based materials modeling at the atomic, meso and continuum scales *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **271** 108171
- Unke O T and Meuwly M 2019 PhysNet: a neural network for predicting energies, forces, dipole moments and partial charges *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **15** 3678–93
- Wang Y, Lv J, Zhu Li and Ma Y 2012 Calypso: a method for crystal structure prediction *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **183** 2063–70
- Wines D, Garrity K F, Xie T and Choudhary K 2023 Forward and inverse design of high T_c superconductors with DFT and deep learning *Workshop on "Machine Learning for Materials" ICLR 2023*
- Wróbel J S, Nguyen-Manh D, Lavrentiev M Y, Muzyk M and Dudarev S L 2015 Phase stability of ternary FCC and BCC Fe-Cr-Ni alloys *Phys. Rev. B* **91** 024108
- Wu C, Lee B-J and Su. X 2017 Modified embedded-atom interatomic potential for Fe-Ni, Cr-Ni and Fe-Cr-Ni systems *Calphad* **57** 98–106
- Wu Q, He B, Song T, Gao J and Shi S 2016 Cluster expansion method and its application in computational materials science *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **125** 243–54
- Xiao G, Yang W, Zhu Q, Song S, Cao G-H and Ren Z 2023 Superconductivity with large upper critical field in noncentrosymmetric Cr-bearing high-entropy alloys *Scr. Mater.* **223** 115099
- Xie T, Fu X, Ganea O-E, Barzilay R and Jaakkola T 2022 Crystal diffusion variational autoencoder for periodic material generation (arXiv:2110.06197)
- Yeh J-W, Chen S-K, Lin S-J, Gan J-Y, Chin T-S, Shun T-T, Tsau C-H and Chang S-Y 2004 Nanostructured high-entropy alloys with multiple principal elements: novel alloy design concepts and outcomes *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **6** 299–303
- Zeni C et al 2024 Mattergen: a generative model for inorganic materials design (arXiv:2312.03687)
- Zhang R, Zhao S, Ding J, Chong Y, Jia T, Ophus C, Asta M, Ritchie R O and Minor A M 2020 Short-range order and its impact on the CrCoNi medium-entropy alloy *Nature* **581** 283–7
- Zhao Y, Al-Fahdi M, Hu M, Siriwardane E M D, Song Y, Nasiri A and Hu. J 2021 High-throughput discovery of novel cubic crystal materials using deep generative neural networks *Adv. Sci.* **8** 2100566